

Analysis of placement & examination assistance platform

Shreya Srivastava^{1,*}, Moonmoon Roy², Sakshi Agarwal³ and Amit Kumar Tiwari⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Department Of Computer Science & Engineering, United Institute of Technology, Prayagraj, Uttar Pradesh, India

Received: 18 April 2022

Accepted: 16 May 2022

Published Online:

18 May 2022

© The Author(s) 2022

ABSTRACT

Highly growing telecommunication infrastructures, which include the Internet, and the development of high performance have appeared in a new era of rapid advances in Information Technology (IT). The Internet has become a plethora of information concerning any aspect which has existed in this world. There is so much information present on every topic that a student cannot understand what is important and what they can skip. Thus, a platform is needed where students can get effective exposure, synergy, and a right route closer to communication and can share their experiences about their college life, events that happen in their college, their ideas, and ways to get through the process of selection in different companies and anything that they found can improve and make college life easier. Here the process of knowledge sharing is concerned with the purity of the facts and statistics collected from various attested sources. We aim to help ardent mass to share their ideas with purity and truth where different users can interact with each other on various issues.

Keywords

Internet, Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC), Model, Semester and Sessional Exams, Interview

Heading Editor: Satheesh Kumar

*Address Correspondence to E-mail: shreyasrivastava121999@gmail.com

I. INTRODUCTION

Every student searches for notes and previous year's papers to prepare well for any examination be it mid-term or semester examinations, but when the time arrives for making new notes for preparation, students might get into the confusion that what is important and what is not, as when the examination is near everything seems to be important. Also, when appearing for any placements or drives, everyone wishes to talk to their seniors or talk to people placed in their dream companies to get advice for preparations regarding interviews [1]. Thus, having a website where students can post notes, previous year's question papers, their interview experiences, and other students can perform activities like view, like, or comment on it would save a lot of time and will increase students interest in studying and discussing academic and useful information.

A platform may reduce hardships faced by the students during preparation. It may provide a simple interface where students can log in using their ID and password and can see all the posts related to academics or events in their college. It can be used by colleges or any educational institution to preserve documents easily. The formulation and management of precise, detailed, and updated information regarding a student's academic career are of top importance to universities and colleges [2]. This information system regarding students deals with all kinds of academic-associated reports like previous years questionnaires, curriculum, placement information, and other resource-related news too. This platform will connect the users to the relevant audience and content. It will also make users aware of the registration and deadlines of various hackathons, coding contests, technical events, seminars, etc.

There are various sources/sites which offer interview questions and previous year papers of multiple companies and universities to help the ones preparing for placements and examinations but those existing sources are reliable only to an extent and it takes a lot of time to search the right and useful content of one's need [3]. For interview questions, one needs to look at different sites while for semester papers into a different site. Hence, there is a need for a common platform that fulfils all the requirements.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Nowadays, online studies are so much promoted and adopted by everyone that every student is searching for the right study material on the internet. Internet is an ocean of information, for everything [4]. There are various sites and resources available which makes students confused and unfocused. Sometimes the availability of more than the required sites and material of knowledge on the internet makes students mess up with content which leads to collecting wrong knowledge and also kills a lot of their useful time. Some of the certain common issues are stated below.

- Students get a limited period for preparation for any examination and hence, it is not possible to look and read from every site available on the internet related to the searched topic.
- The information gathered from the internet is not always authentic and correct and can be trusted only to a certain extent [5].
- Having more than the required information about any searched topic creates confusion and distraction.
- It takes more time to visit different sites and search different topics like the previous year's semester question paper and interview experiences. One has to visit two different sites for the same topic.

Another common problem noticed among students is that they are not well informed or do not have proper awareness about the different hackathons, coding competitions, cultural fest dates, etc, and hence they miss the deadlines of registrations and are not able to participate in them [6].

III. METHODOLOGY

Software Development Life Cycle (SDLC) is a procedure in Fig. 1 observed for a software project, within a software firm. It consists of a detailed plan that describes how to develop, maintain, replace, alter, or improve particular software. This life cycle defines a methodology for enhancing software to its best and the overall process of development.

Fig. 1SDLC Phases

There are multiple software development models defined and drafted which are incorporated during the process of software development. Following are the most important and popular SDLC models followed in the enterprise:

- Waterfall Model
- Iterative Model
- Spiral Model
- RAD Model
- Incremental Model

A. Comparison of SDLC Models

There are various SDLC models to suit the needs of the project:

- Waterfall Model: Not possible to return to an earlier phase | Only for small projects | Not flexible to changes | High-risk involvement
- Spiral Model: Possible to return to an earlier phase | Expensive cost | Requires typical maintenance | Medium to high risk | Testing after every iteration
- RAD Model: User involvement only at the beginning | Not suitable for high technical risk | Requires highly skilled developers

- Incremental Model: Low cost | Flexible to changes | Promotes maintainability | Promotes the quick release of the product
- Prototype Model: Increase in cost of development | Time and efforts wasted in making prototypes again and again

B. Selection of SDLC Model-Incremental Model

After comparing different types of models, we have selected the best-suited model as the Incremental model for this project as our requirements are superior and it is a long-developing project.

C. Incremental Model

The incremental model in Fig. 2 is an action of software evolution where requirements are divided into multiple independent modules of the software development cycle. In this model, each module transcends the requirements, design, implementation, and testing phases. Every subsequent release of the module has the ability to add a function to its preceding release. The process continues until the complete system is attained.

Fig. 2 Incremental Model

D. Reason to select the Incremental model

We have selected this model because this model is used in the following conditions which are matching the requirements of our idea and there are also many advantages of this model.

- Used when the requirements are advanced.
- Project has a prolonged development agenda.
- Software teams are less experienced or incompetent.
- You can broaden those requirements first which have higher priority.

Advantages are:

- Building and improving the product step by step.
- Testing and debugging in small iterations are easier.
- Any change in requirements can be easily done.
- Risk is examined and identified in each iteration.
- As the product is split into smaller chunks it is easier to manage the product.
- Defects are discovered rapidly.
- Progress can be measured.

IV. TECHNICAL ANALYSIS

A technology stack is a collection of tools and frameworks used to develop, run and grow a software product. Stacks may be used for building web applications in a short time because they reduce efforts and development time. The stack used for developing web applications is the acknowledgment of software engineers to modern needs and current demands.

MERN is one of the most admired and accepted stacks that have been derived from JavaScript. It comprises open source components and offers a framework for building web-based applications that enable browsers to connect with databases.

- MERN comprises MongoDB, ExpressJS, ReactJS, and NodeJS as its key technologies.
- MongoDB: A document-oriented database capable of handling all types of unstructured and complicated data. It is easily scalable and has high performance.
- ExpressJS: Express is a Node.js web framework that manages servers and routes.
- ReactJS: A front-end library used to build reusable UI components of a single-page web application. It is developed by Facebook and uses JSX.
- NodeJS: A JavaScript runtime environment that allows one to run JavaScript on a server rather than in a browser.

A. Designing

During the design phase, developers or solution architects draft the high-level design of the software or the overall system design to be able to deliver every requirement of the user. This is one of the most important phases in the development life cycle of a system because it involves the conversion of the abstract design of the system into a physical layout.

B. Data Flow Diagram

The purpose of a DFD in [Fig. 3](#) is to show the graphical representation of data flow, scope, and boundaries for any process or system. There are various levels in DFD like 0, 1, 2, or more.

Fig. 3 DFD Level 0

C. Use Case Diagram

A Use Case diagram in Fig. 4 & 5 depicts various use cases and different types of users involved in the system. It contains elements like actors, use cases, and the relationship between actors and use cases.

Fig. 4 Admin: Use Case

Fig. 5 User: Use Case

D. ER-Diagram

ER diagram in Fig. 6 is useful in creating and maintaining databases.

Fig. 6 ER Diagram

V. WORKING

Any Student having the following essentials can access the website:

- Web browser
- Internet Connection
- User ID and Password

E. Flowchart

A flowchart in [Fig. 7](#) that depicts an approach to performing a task through a sequence of steps.

The following flow chart describes the working of our system.

Fig. 7 Flow chart

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

This platform supports automating and improving the prevailing systems. It reduces the manpower required and provides authentic and meticulous information to advance decision-making. All the information gathered can be saved and retrieved at any time from the database. Therefore, the data stored in the repository helps in taking decisions regarding curriculum, interview, or placement by the students. All the students can get the required information hassle-free. This system is crucial in colleges and universities and will be very efficient and less time-consuming due to the care taken to develop it. It is worthy to state that the system has the ability to cope with any erroneous input. Provision is also made for future development in this system for further growth.

However, there is always room for improvement in any application or website. In the future, it may be extended to include features such as:

- Video and audio messages
- Bookmarking important posts
- Posting GIFs, and stickers along with comments

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

We would like to thank our principal, Mr. Sanjay Srivastava and our HOD Mr. Abhishek Malaviya for granting us the opportunity to work in this field. We would like to express the deep sense of gratitude to our seniors for their important help and suggestions. We are also very thankful to all the members of the CSE Department lab who have directly or indirectly contributed to this research work.

REFERENCES

1. Nilesh Bhad, Pooja Kamble, Sunita Saini, Prof. Yogesh Thorat, "An Interactive Online Training and Placement System", International Journal of Advanced Research Development, Vol. 3, Issue 11, 2016.
2. Swati Choudhary, Monica Landge, Shital Salunke, Swarupata Sutar, Kirti M hamunkar, "Advanced training and Placement Web Portal", International Journal of Technical Research and Applications e-ISSN: 2320-8163, www.ijtra.com Volume 4, Issue 2 (March-April, 2016), PP. 75-77
3. Liu, Yang, et al. "The Application of Data Mining Techniques in College Students Information System." *2018 International Conference on Computer Science, Electronics and Communication Engineering (CSECE 2018)*. Atlantis Press, 2018.
4. Rathore, Ravi Kumar, and J. Jayanthi. "Student Prediction System for Placement Training using Fuzzy Inference System." *ICTACT Journal on Soft Computing* 7.3 (2017): 1443-1446.
5. Priyanka Hajare, Priyanka Khandave, Shital Adhav, Swati Pimpale, Prof. Anagha Kulkarni "Implementation of Online Placement System", International Journal of Emerging Research in Management & Technology, Volume-5, Issue-1, 2016.
6. Ayodele O.A. and Absalom E.E. "Design and Implementation of Students' Information System for Tertiary Institutions using Neural Networks: An Open Source Approach", International Journal of Green Computing, Vol. 1, No. 1, pp. 1-15(2010).